

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE CLINICAL COURSE OF CHRONIC CHOLECYSTITIS BASED ON COMORBIDITY IN THE GERONT- SUPERGERONT POPULATION OF THE OASIS, DIRECTIONS FOR PREVENTION

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Relevance and necessity of the topic. Scientific observations devoted to solving cholecystitis and its therapeutic and surgical problems were carried out in the population of different ages [1; 2; 3; 4].

Conservative treatment of cholecystitis is ineffective in up to 80%, and as a result, surgery is performed against the background of complications. For this reason, mortality in geront clients exceeds 40-50% [5]. Development and improvement of geronto-cholecystitis screening methods, algorithms and programs for early detection and prevention, taking into account existing comorbid diseases and characteristics of cholecystitis, is considered an urgent issue and necessity.

The aim of the research is to study and determine the epidemiological, clinical and preventive characteristics of cholecystitis in the young, middle-aged, geront and supergeront populations of different regions of Uzbekistan.

Materials and research methods. This study is considered a simultaneous epidemiological investigation and it is based on the analysis of the results obtained in a population of 2682 people. Residents of 6 regions of the country - Andijan, Namangan, Fergana, Jizzakh, Syrdarya and Kashkadarya - were involved in the study. Based on the tasks set in the work, 6 simultaneous epidemiological studies were organized and carried out in the valley and oasis regions of Uzbekistan.

A detailed description of the organization and conduct of the epidemiological study was provided: the screening group was formed, questionnaires were prepared, and the screening group was introduced to the necessary equipment for the study. A procedure for working with the population was created and a procedure for checking the population was developed.

Results and Discussions. The features of the clinical course of chronic cholecystitis in the geront and supergeront population in the oasis region were

studied on the basis of comorbidity (11 different) and the priority objects of prevention were determined.

Comorbidity of chronic cholecystitis was not noted in the supergeront population of the oasis (due to the absence of a supergeront population).

Based on various comorbidities, chronic cholecystitis, cholecystitis without stones and cholecystitis with stones were recorded in the following distribution frequencies in accordance with regional specificity: 1) in steatohepatitis comorbidity - per 9.5%, 7.1% and 2.4%; 2) chronic viral comorbidity - 6.7%, 3.4% and 3.4%; 3) in viral liver cirrhosis comorbidity - per 0.00% and 0.00%; 4) in comorbidity of acute ischemic heart disease - per 7.1%, 5.9% and 1.2%; 5) in comorbidity of chronic ischemic heart disease - per 7.0%, 4.9% and 2.1%; 6) in glomerular comorbidity - from 20.8%, 18.3% and 2.5%; 7) in gastroenterological comorbidity - per 10.6%, 7.1% and 3.5%; 8) when neurocirculatory asthenia is a comorbidity of chronic cholecystitis - per 5.6%, 2.8% and 2.8%; 9) in comorbidity of joint diseases - per 7.1%, 5.3% and 1.9%; 10) in comorbidity of respiratory diseases - per 3.6%, 3.6% and 0.0%; 11) on the basis of comorbidity with anemia - per 11.7%, 8.9% and 2.8%; 12) on the basis of total comorbidity (n=1613/0) – per 9.0%, 6.6% and 2.4%.

Anemic comorbidity (risk 11.7%), glomerular comorbidity (risk 20.8%) and gastroenterological comorbidity (risk level - 10.6%) are confirmed as a leading role in increasing the risk of clinical course of chronic cholecystitis in the geront population under Oasis conditions.

Conclusion. In general, it was confirmed that the risk of chronic cholecystitis (severe type, complicated form) increases by at least 9.0% on the basis of comorbidity in the population of gerontological age of the Oasis.

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